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3	KCL	KING'S COLLEGE LONDON	United Kingdom
4	NUI GALWAY	NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND GALWAY	Ireland
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	SORBONNE	SORBONNE UNIVERSITE (LinkedTP)	France
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Project Summary

European musical heritage is a dynamic historical flow of experiences, leaving heterogeneous traces that are difficult to capture, connect, access, interpret, and valorise. Computing technologies have the potential to shed a light on this wealth of resources by extracting, materialising and linking new knowledge from heterogeneous sources, hence revealing facts and experiences from hidden voices of the past. Polifonia makes this happen by building novel ways of inspecting, representing, and interacting with digital content. Memory institutions, scholars, and citizens will be able to navigate, explore, and discover multiple perspectives and stories about European Musical Heritage.

Polifonia focuses on European Musical Heritage, intended as musical contents and artefacts - or music objects - (tunes, scores, melodies, notations, etc.) along with relevant knowledge about them such as: their links to tangible objects (theatres, conservatoires, churches, etc.), their cultural and historical contexts, opinions and stories told by people having diverse social and artistic roles (scholars, writers, students, intellectuals, musicians, politicians, journalists, etc), and facts expressed in different styles and disciplines (memoire, reportage, news, biographies, reviews), different languages (English, Italian, French, Spanish, and German), and across centuries.

The overall goal of the project is to realise an ecosystem of computational methods and tools supporting discovery, extraction, encoding, interlinking, classification, exploration of, and access to, musical heritage knowledge on the Web. An equally important objective is to demonstrate that these tools improve the state of the art of Social Science and Humanities (SSH) methodologies. Hence their development is guided by, and continuously intertwined with, experiments and validations performed in real-world settings, identified by musical heritage stakeholders (both belonging to the Consortium and external supporters) such as cultural institutes and collection owners, historians of music, anthropologists and ethnomusicologists, linguists, etc.

Executive Summary

The INTERLINK pilot aims at connecting knowledge graphs of European musical cultural heritage, which are notoriously large and use a diversified vocabulary of relations. The pilot is not bound to the specific institutional dataset, collections or use cases; but rather summarises the common needs of all pilots of representing their data as music knowledge graphs, and develop technologies that will enable finding new meaningful connections among them. Initial efforts were devoted at creating ChoCo – the largest knowledge graph of music harmony, and harmonising the stakeholders' requirements into the Polifonia Ontology Network – to facilitate entity linking and ontology alignment upfront. This provided the infrastructure and the requirements to address the final challenge of the pilot: i.e. linking knowledge graphs at scale.

As pointed in the previous versions of the deliverable, existing work in the relevant areas of knowledge engineering, knowledge graph construction, and knowledge graph interlinking is promising but presents a number of pitfalls in its direct application to Polifonia from the point of view of achieving this knowledge graph building and interlinking that necessitates scalability, inductiveness, and computational efficiency. Learning numerical representations from knowledge graphs is currently the most prominent approach to address *link prediction*, in addition to knowledge discovery and reasoning tasks. This is often done by allocating and learning embedding tables for all (or a subset of) the entities. As this scales linearly with the number of entities, learning embedding models in real-world KGs with millions of entities is computationally intractable.

This deliverable describes our efforts delivering a novel method for knowledge graph embeddings that: (i) only allocates embedding tables for relations (which are typically orders of magnitude fewer than the entities) and requires less than 50% of the parameters of previous parameter efficient methods; (ii) rather than storing entity embeddings, it learns to compute them – by leveraging multiple entity-relation paths to contextualise individual entities within triples. Evaluated on various benchmarks, our method achieves significant results on path-rich KGs and can yield state-of-the-art performance for link prediction while training on consumer-grade hardware. We perform ablation experiments to analyse the sensitivity of our model to key hyper-parameters, and provide insights into its applicability based on specific KG properties. To contextualise our work, we discuss (a) how a scalable methodology for link prediction is well suited for the requirements and the long-term vision of Polifonia; and (b) our future plans for applying our method to the Polifonia Knowledge Graphs to interlink them with large resources (Wikidata).

Finally, to complement our vision, we also report a novel computation method for modelling musical influence – which enables the detection of creative influence between artists using techniques based on graph theory and complex network science. As this method takes into account the individuality of a relationship type, this provides a powerful tool to infer further links within and across music knowledge graphs.

Document History

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1 Introduction

Knowledge graphs (KGs) such as Wikidata and Freebase serve as a structured embodiment of human knowledge in machine readable format. A KG consists of a large number of (`subject`, `relation`, `predicate`) triples, where subject and predicate (alias *head* and *tail*) are nodes in the KG and the relation is the edge connecting them. Each triple denotes an atomic fact, such as (`London`, `capital_of`, `England`). KGs are currently ubiquitous and are used in question answering, information retrieval [1], recommendation systems [2], autonomous agents [3] and have also recently been used to complement Large Language Models (LLMs) with facts and common sense knowledge [4] from authoritative sources.

A central mission of Polifonia is to build and interlink knowledge graphs of European musical cultural heritage. These interconnected KGs act as a *data backbone* for the project, not just as a form of a dynamic and schema-free database that can be easily used in pilots, demonstrations, prototypes, or the Web Portal; but also as a proper contribution and project output for other stakeholders to repurpose and reuse. Knowledge graphs have been successfully deployed for solving problems of data interoperability and integration in various domains [5] (e.g. Web search, healthcare, science, etc.), and in Polifonia we develop them further to also address these issues in the interesting, albeit disconnected and often siloed, data collections that hold our European musical cultural heritage. Examples include ChoCo [6], a musical harmony KG contributed in INTERLINK that integrates 18 different chord datasets and provides an integration workflow for music annotation datasets; but also Harmony [7], reusing the scale of ChoCo to find pattern-level harmonic similarities among pieces (from different sources). Overall, KGs have the potential to be the technical archetype to help us discover their hidden connections and relationships.

So far, our work in INTERLINK has addressed the problem of content-based music linking. In addition, we have also analysed and harmonised the requirements of all pilots in the Polifonia Ontology Network [8]. By reusing the same ontologies, Polifonia's KGs are easier to link by design (e.g. aligning two entities is attempted only if they are instances of the same class). Building and interlinking knowledge graphs¹ is not new, and is regarded as a knowledge completion task. Even when considered individually, a KG is often incomplete, which means that information (triples) are missing from the graph; including those triples that implement equivalence statements for entity linking. To alleviate this issue, researchers and practitioners have developed several methods, with the most prominent one being learning of Knowledge Graph embeddings, either by storing the learned representations in embedding tables or by utilising more complex GNN architectures. In Machine Learning, learning embedding is a fundamental task in Representation Learning. The field deals with designing computational models, paradigms, and training objectives to learn

¹We use the phrase *interlinking knowledge graphs* in a broad sense, covering the *enrichment* of such conversion by establishing new links that otherwise would have not been available at KG construction time.

Figure 1.1: Entity alignment as a special task of link and relation prediction.

numerical representation (alias embeddings) that can be reused for a number of downstream tasks and applications. For example, in NLP, pre-trained text embeddings are used as starting point for semantic search, paraphrase detection, sentiment analysis, syntactic parsing, etc. In the KG domain, embeddings provide good performance in completion tasks but suffer from significant drawbacks, namely the fact that they do not scale to Web-scale knowledge graphs of millions or billions of nodes and that they lack the capacity to produce embeddings of new nodes without being retrained from scratch. For instance, methods based on Graph Neural Networks require storing the whole network at runtime; nodes corresponds to neurons from which convolutions are defined via message passing. This makes current state of the art methods intractable for large datasets, which aligns with Polifonia’s requirements given the knowledge graphs that have been contributed in the project, and the goal of interlinking them with external Web resources (e.g. Wikidata), which in turn adds computational and memory complexity.

In our case, as the goal is to find missing links within and across KGs, we focus on embedding methods that can be used for *relation prediction* and *link prediction*. The former aims at predicting the relation(s) that may exist between head and tail entities – hence completing the triple $(h, ?, t)$. Link prediction is of more general scope, as it aims at predicting either the head entity h given the incomplete triple $(?, r, t)$; or analogously, the tail entity t from $(h, r, ?)$. As illustrated in Figure 1.1, linking knowledge graphs via entity alignment is a specialisation of link and relation prediction when e.g. $r = owl:sameAs$; where the starting point is either a couple of entities that are supposedly equivalent (relation prediction), or focuses on an initial entity regardless of it being a head or a tail (given the transitive property of equivalence relations such as $owl:sameAs$).

1.1 Our contribution

Given the limitations of current embedding methods, we propose a novel embedding model that aims to address the scalability and inductive embedding problems faced by current methods. Specifically, our model aims to (i) address the scalability requirement by only storing relation representations and learning to compute entity representation by designing a model architecture

that draws inspiration by sequence models; (ii) leverage path information to contextualise nodes and the connectivity patterns between them aiming to produce useful structure aware entity representations without having to conduct message passing across the entire graph as GNNs do; (iii) address the inductive embedding of new nodes by only using relations and paths to calculate node embeddings, thus being able to produce embeddings for new nodes without additional training. Our results demonstrate that (i) relations provide sufficient information to learn effective KG representations; while (ii) leveraging path information results in competitive performance with increased scalability and parameter efficiency.

In relation to previous deliverables, we draw contextualise our contributions as follows.

- D1.5 [9] reported our endeavours to create and evaluate ChoCo [6], which focused on the interconnection of music annotation datasets, with a specific focus on harmonic annotations. This deliverable instead, is of more general applicability and contributes methods for linking datasets that already exist in the form of KGs. Being able to create music knowledge graphs from annotation datasets, integrating them despite their formats, and now, interconnecting them with other KGs within and beyond Polifonia concludes our vision for the pilot and opens up new opportunities for the exploitation of our resources.
- D2.2 [10] documented the creation of the Polifonia Ontology Network (PON) and the new methodologies we contributed to facilitate and streamline the process of requirement engineering. Here we remark how the reuse of PON across pilots is preparatory for linking, as it creates opportunities to express knowledge consistently using the same set of relations and classes. As discussed in Section 3.4, this is a central requirement for the applicability of the method presented in this document. In addition, deliverable D2.2 also contributed methods for finding links between harmonic progressions, based on segment-level similarities, and their potential reuse for knowledge discovery and computational creativity. In the context of this deliverable, where we aim at finding links from structural patterns in a KG, the ability to find links at the musical content level provides opportunities to leverage the specificity and the multimodality of our KGs (specifically, ChoCo [6] and Harmory [7]).

Combining and integrating different musical resources results in a large knowledge base that can be used for several different tasks. An important aspect to be considered the analysis of the produced Knowledge Graph to make tacit knowledge emerge explicitly. The field of complex network analysis has a long history of proposed methods and techniques, generally based on graph theory. Those methods provide the means to quantitatively measure the structural properties of a network. In Section 4 we explore the centrality of nodes in a graph and the number of redundant connections between nodes to compute the creative influence between two artists.

2 Related Work

Interlinking knowledge graphs to find connections to external entities across the Web, has been one of the paramount problems addressed by the Semantic Web community [11]. As the original focus of the community was on building and publishing ontologies in a distributed manner, the field of ontology matching emerged as a solution to the problem of their interlinking. Specifically, ontology matching aims at finding correspondences between semantically related entities of different ontologies. These correspondences may stand for equivalence as well as other relations, such as consequence, subsumption, or disjointness, between ontology entities [12]. As the field turned more towards data engineering work with Linked Data and knowledge graphs, the interlinking problem was viewed under the prism of identity resolution, i.e. to find semantically identical entities among different RDF knowledge graphs to link through the `owl:sameAs` property [5]. However, such a strong identity definition implies logical entailments sometimes erroneous; various approaches exist to detect such erroneous identity links, by e.g. using network metrics and community detection algorithms [13].

More recently, the interlinking problem has been studied under the prism of knowledge graph link prediction, primarily by using machine learning and neural network architectures [5].

2.1 Knowledge Graph Embeddings

Several methods have been developed to perform link prediction and other KG related tasks. These methods can be broadly divided into logical rule mining, path-based reasoning, meta-relational learning and embedding based methods. Rule mining methods and path-based reasoning methods suffer from poor scalability given that the number of rules and paths increases exponentially with the size of the graph, while meta-relational methods focus on the task of performing predictions on previously unseen nodes and rely on traditional embedding methods for producing embeddings for known nodes. Embedding based methods have become the most prominent because they produce the best performance while being scalable to larger KGs and being able to be used as input to other ML models, as has been investigated recently in KG-enhanced LLMs. The main limitation of embedding based methods is that they encode each node and relation as separate vectors, which produces two undesired outcomes. The first is that as the size of the KG grows so does the embedding table making the use of these methods on real-world KGs with several million or billions of entities intractable (e.g. Wikidata currently counts 11K+ relation types and 108M+ entities). The second drawback is that the embedding tables are computed during training and as such addition of new entities cannot be accommodated without retraining the model on the entire KG.

2.2 Parameter Efficient Representations

Aiming to overcome these issues, recent works have focused on reducing the amount of information that is stored and using only the relations and the stored information to encode entities, thus finding a balance between memory requirement and performance, while maintaining the inductive bias of relations. Such works include Nodepiece [14] and EARL [15]. Nodepiece uses a fixed vocabulary of entity embeddings, called anchors and combines these embeddings, the distances (hops) between anchors and entities in the KG and their relational context to encode them. Although this method is scalable to large KGs, and works in the inductive setting by utilising only the relational context, this comes at a performance cost of performance (it is worse than RotatE) which is a traditional embedding method. Instead, EARL uses relations along with a fixed vocabulary of entity embeddings called reserved entities and the similarity between relational contexts of reserved entities and every other entity to compute entity representations. This approach has the ability to inductively embed unseen nodes, achieves better parameter efficiency and outperforms Nodepiece. However, it relies on GNNs, hence facing scalability issues with large KGs.

2.3 Path-based embedding methods

Significant work has focused on using paths mined from the Knowledge Graph to perform link and relation prediction. Indeed, the work of [16] on Neural Bellman-Ford Networks showed that utilising paths between nodes and a generalized composition and addition operator can achieve competitive performance on link prediction but it performs only link prediction and does not produce representations of entities that can be used for other tasks. Moreover, in their work, [17] proposed DIVA, which uses relational paths and achieves state-of-the-art performance in relation prediction. Finally, given that classic embedding methods only exploit direct relations between entities, there have been numerous research works leveraging the multi-step semantics contained in relational paths to produce improved performance in link prediction. These include PTransE [18] which leverages paths up to length 3 and introduces the path constrained resource allocation algorithm to measure the reliability of paths, PaSKoGE [19] which builds upon PTransE and proposes an automated way of calculating the margin hyperparameter for the loss function, DPTransE [20] which extends PTransE by using clustering to group together relation types and calculate the weights of paths, while using relation-group specific classifiers to score triples. Furthermore, [21], [22] and [23] all use composition operators to combine path elements into a single representation, [24, 25] and [26] first mine logical rules which they convert to paths and use them in conjunction with traditional embeddings to perform link prediction, while [27] and [28] use recurrent models to combine path elements in a single representation. Finally, [29] developed PathCon which is a method utilizing relational paths combined with a Graph neural network to perform relation prediction and achieves state-of-the-art performance on the task. Unfortunately, all of those methods either use paths in conjunction with non-scalable traditional embedding methods and/or mine multiple paths between the head and the tail entity of each triple. Mining multiple paths between the head and tail of each triple is computationally prohibitive in larger KGs, especially when

the evaluation of the models requires the scoring of each true triple against every possible false triple resulting in (no. of triples x no. of entities) triples to score. Furthermore, the embeddings produced for each entity are contextualized to the triple, hence storing them becomes intractable.

2.4 Influence prediction

Evaluating the influences of an artist, and in particular of a composer or a musician, is mostly considered a subjective task. Usually, experts analyse the compositions of an artist in a critical way to relate them to other important artists. One approach to detecting creative influence is to directly analyse explicit influence connections, curated by human annotators. [30], for example, analyses the influences identified in the Classical Music Navigator (CMS) to better understand the influence of the composers in the dataset. A similar approach is taken by [31], where the data on creative influence is used to investigate the similarity of musical compositions.

Relying on similarity as a proxy for creative influence is a popular approach that has been explored using different techniques. [32] define a framework where influence can be modelled using a graph structure. Edges are added to the graph by taking into account the similarity between the two artworks. Several works have explored this approach in the visual art domain with promising results [33, 34]. and in the musical domain. [35] models the influence of musical composition as the probability of success of a composition given its similarity to other popular compositions. In [36], the influence of a composer on another composer is measured as the degree of similarity between their compositions. A composer is classified as influential when musical features of its compositions are re-used by other composers.

Relying on artefact similarity, however, can be a problematic approach in art. Influence can affect an artist in a negative way, in the sense that the influenced artist deliberately abstains from his influence [37]. These kinds of artists are sometimes defined as deviant artists [38, 39]. [40] investigates similarity with respect to socio-cultural indicators, such as geographical and temporal location or organisational system in which the artist lives. Findings suggest that highly embedded individuals, i.e. individuals with a dense social network, are more likely to produce novel artefacts that can be influential to other artists. [41] analyses influence of the *teacher-student* relationship through a combination of artifact features. Albeit with different intensities, findings highlight the importance of such a relationship, as also observed in [42]. Analysing the social network of artists using complex network tools has been explored in literature [34, 43, 44]. The relationships taken into account are often the result of heuristic methods or are limited to a few relationship types, such as *teacher-student* or *bandmates*. Relying on a rich social network where different relationship types are taken into account has been proven to be an effective way of uncovering meaningful insights [45] from data. Moreover, considering many different relationship types is an important requirement, as it has been largely discussed how different relationship ties can contribute differently to creative influence [42, 44, 46].

Differently from the described approaches, we investigate the importance of social relationships without taking into account any information on the creative artefact. Our approach can be easily integrated with other methods that use similarity, to yield a more general method for uncovering

hidden relations when perceptual similarity is the only measure taken into account.

3 Learning parameter-efficient KG embeddings

Our methodology to learn scalable and parameter-efficient KG embeddings leverages paths drawn from unique random walks starting or ending from/at each entity (3.1); and takes inspiration from sequence modelling to aggregate and localise information from the corresponding sequences. Instead of explicitly allocating a full embedding table for entities, we only encode relations. Entities can then be encoded by initially expressing them in relation to their relational context, which is defined as the number and type of the relations they appear with (either as head or entail, for outgoing and incoming contexts respectively). Then, a node projector learns to project entity-specific relational context information either by approximating a graph convolution on relational context information or by forwarding this information through a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP); this yields an entity representation that has the same dimension of the relation embeddings (3.2.1). Entity-relation paths can then be constructed by combining node projections and embeddings, respectively. Given a triple (h, r, t) , multiple incoming and outgoing paths for each entity (h, t) are processed by a sequence model (Section 3.2.2); so that an aggregation strategy can be applied across all the entity representations in each path (Section 3.2.3). This yields embedding vectors for head, tail, and relation – which are trained using a learning objective for link prediction or/and relation prediction (Section 3.2.4). The contribution reported in this section is part of a methodological effort that is currently in submission [47].

3.1 Path Generation and Representation

We created training paths by mining random walks from each entity in the KG. For each entity we attempted to mine 20 unique paths with no loops (no nodes in the path appearing more than once). These paths were either outgoing (starting from the node) or incoming (ending at the node) with probability of 50%. The mined paths are both entity and relation paths. Mining paths for each entity in isolation is a deliberate design choice that allows the path mining process to be embarrassingly parallel since no communication is required between processes mining paths for different entities. As such, our path mining implementation is highly parallelised and can easily scale to large KGs. These paths provide information about the neighbourhoods of the entities and are expected to localise them within the KG. Moreover, batching together multiple paths for each entity allows the model to extract information related to the different semantics of the entity as these are represented in the various paths. For example, the path *<Arnold Schwarzenegger, actor in, the Terminator, directed by, James Cameron>* and the path *<Arnold Schwarzenegger, winner of, Mister Olympia, year, 1980>* provide very different semantic information for the entity Arnold Schwarzenegger with each possibly being less or more useful depending on the task at hand. In addition to the random walks sampled from the entities of the KG, for each test triple, 10

paths between the head and tail were mined to provide the connectivity context between the head and tail and provide additional semantic context. The two path types (entity and relation paths) follow different routes within our model, with the entity paths being flattened and passed through the node projector module to produce d-dimensional representations of the entities and the relational paths being passed through an embedding layer and replaced with their d-dimensional learned representations. The d-dimensional representations are interleaved prior to inputting the paths into the transformer model.

3.2 Model architecture

Formally, given a set \mathcal{E} of entities and a set \mathcal{R} of relations, a Knowledge Graph $\mathcal{K} \subseteq (\mathcal{E} \times \mathcal{R} \times \mathcal{E})$ is a directed multi-relational graph that stores domain knowledge in the form of triples, which are also called facts [48]. Each triple (h, r, t) consists of a head entity $h \in \mathcal{E}$, a tail entity $t \in \mathcal{E}$ and the relationship $r \in \mathcal{R}$ between those entities. For simplicity, we denote the number of triples in a batch as Z , the number of paths used to describe an entity as *ppe* (paths-per-entity), and the size of the longest path in the batch as *plen*.

Our model consists of four modules, each with its own functionality and trainable end-to-end. The model architecture begins with the *node projector*, which projects the entities into a continuous space based on their relational context; the *path sequence model* which accepts batches of path sequences and produces contextual representations of entities; the *aggregator* module which aggregates the node representations from the different paths into a single contextualised representation; and, finally, the *prediction heads* which produce a score for each triple or relation depending on the task (we provide prediction heads for relation and link prediction).

3.2.1 Node Projector

For the node projector, we utilise either a modified Graph Convolutional Network (GCN) layer or a two-layer MLP. The modified Graph Convolutional Network (GCN) layer takes as input the local adjacency matrix of the node-edge graph. The node edge graph is a weighted graph created by converting the edges to nodes and adding a directed relation from each edge to a node with weight equal to the number of times this edge appears in the relational context of the node. This results in a simplified and relatively small adjacency matrix $\mathbf{A}_{er} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{E}| \times |\mathcal{R}|}$. Two separate GCN models are utilised, one for incoming and one for outgoing relational context. The node projections are then calculated by utilising a GCN layer consisting of an edge embedding table $\mathbf{E}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{R}| \times d}$ and a square learnable weight matrix $\mathbf{W}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{R}| \times |\mathcal{R}|}$. The full graph convolution operation is thus defined as

$$\mathbf{P} = \mathbf{A}_{er} \mathbf{E}_r \mathbf{W}_r \quad (3.1)$$

where \times denotes a matrix multiplication and $\mathbf{P} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{E}| \times d}$. While this approach allows the GCN layer to scale linearly with the number of nodes in the graph, it has a drawback: during message passing, the only relations that are taken into consideration are the ones that the node is directly

Figure 3.1: Overview of the architecture of our KG embedding model.

connected to. To somewhat alleviate this issue and provide the model with the flexibility to consider relations without direct connections to the nodes, we also introduce an attention module, which accepts as input the adjacency matrix $\mathbf{A}_{er} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{E}| \times |\mathcal{R}|}$ and produces a matrix $\mathbf{Att} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{E}| \times |\mathcal{R}|}$ with the attention that should be applied to each of the relations when message passing. The attention layer is implemented as two-layer Multi-Layer Perceptron and the attention operation is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{Att} = \text{Softmax}(\mathbf{W}_2 \text{Relu}(\mathbf{W}_1 \mathbf{A}_{er} + \mathbf{b}_1) + \mathbf{b}_2). \quad (3.2)$$

As such, the final representation produced by each GCN are calculated as follows:

$$\mathbf{P} = \text{Softmax}(\mathbf{W}_2 \text{Relu}(\mathbf{W}_1 \mathbf{A}_{er} + \mathbf{b}_1) + \mathbf{b}_2) \mathbf{E}_r \mathbf{W}_r \quad (3.3)$$

The representations produced for the incoming \mathbf{P}_{in} and outgoing \mathbf{P}_{out} contexts are then fused together through a two-layer MLP and projected to $\mathbf{P} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{E}| \times d}$ through the operation

$$\mathbf{P} = \mathbf{W}_2 \text{Relu}(\mathbf{W}_1 (\mathbf{P}_{in} | \mathbf{P}_{out}) + \mathbf{b}_1) + \mathbf{b}_2 \quad (3.4)$$

where $|$ denotes the concatenation operator among the corresponding contexts.

Similarly, for the MLP projector we utilise a separate projector for the incoming and outgoing context of nodes. The input of the MLP is the adjacency matrix \mathbf{A}_{er} and the output is a matrix $\mathbf{P} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{E}| \times d}$ with the following operation:

$$\mathbf{P} = \mathbf{W}_2 \text{Relu}(\mathbf{W}_1 \mathbf{A}_{er} + \mathbf{b}_1) + \mathbf{b}_2 \quad (3.5)$$

The representations produced for the incoming \mathbf{P}_{in} and outgoing \mathbf{P}_{out} contexts are then fused together as shown in Equation 3.4.

3.2.2 Path Modelling

Path modelling is operated via a self-attention layer (specifically, a Transformer) which accepts as input a batch of paths $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{R}^{paths \times plen \times d}$, where $paths = Z \times ppe \times 2$. Each path consists of nodes and edges which are projected into a continuous space \mathbb{R}^d using the node projector and an embedding layer respectively.

To let the model better understand where the head and tail entities are located within the paths, a learned positional encoding is added to each embedding vector in the path, based on its position in the sequence. For instance, for an entity path e_0, e_1, \dots, e_n where $e_i \in \mathcal{E}$ and $n = 9$ where the head appears as the 5th element, we consider the following positional encodings for the path

$$[5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6]$$

and add the corresponding embedding of each position (instead of using $[1, 2, \dots, 10]$). Our entity-focused positional encodings can be seen as a path-level contextualisation of [49], which in turn improves the cyclical positional encoding of [50]. This also comes with the advantage of potentially learning to discount the contribution/relevance of entities that are far from the head or tail. Paths are then passed through the transformer, which attends to all the elements of the sequence and produces the path-contextualised projections using all the elements (no masking is used).

3.2.3 Path Aggregator

After sequences (paths) are passed through the Transformer, the output representations are a tensor of shape $\mathbf{B}_{out} \in \mathbb{R}^{paths \times plen \times d}$. Basically, for each path, every entity and relation has an embedding vector of size d . From the output, the representations of the head and tail are selected across all entity-specific paths, and the two resulting tensors are denoted as $\mathbf{B}_{head}, \mathbf{B}_{tail} \in \mathbb{R}^{Z \times ppe \times d}$. These representations are then aggregated into a single relation-contextualised multi-path representation. For this, we experiment with two aggregation strategies: (i) simply averaging the entity vectors; or (ii) using a multi-head attention layer [50]. To implement the latter, we use a matrix of $\mathbf{R}_{head}, \mathbf{R}_{tail} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{R}| \times d}$ as the query vectors and the $\mathbf{B}_{head}, \mathbf{B}_{tail}$ as keys and values. For example, for the head entities, aggregation is performed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} MultiHead(\mathbf{R}_{head}, \mathbf{B}_{head}, \mathbf{B}_{head}) &= Concat(head_1, \dots, head_h) \mathbf{W}^O \\ head_i &= Attention(\mathbf{R}_{head} \mathbf{W}_i^Q, \mathbf{B}_{head} \mathbf{W}_i^K, \mathbf{B}_{head} \mathbf{W}_i^V). \end{aligned} \quad (3.6)$$

We use a traditional dot-product attention mechanism between query and key vectors, as follows

$$Attention(Q, K, V) = softmax\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V \quad (3.7)$$

where $\sqrt{d_k}$ is the dimension of the key vector k and query vector q . The output of the multi-head attention layer is a matrix of relation-contextualised representations for each entity $\mathbf{Agg} \in \mathbb{R}^{Z \times |\mathcal{R}| \times d}$. In the following, we assume that multi-head attention is the default aggregation strategy, as the relational contextualisation provides a generalisation of the averaging for this operation. Using average pooling to perform entity aggregation would be equivalent to assigning an equal weight to all path-contextualised representations of each entity and simplifies the shape of the resulting tensor to $\mathbb{R}^{Z \times d}$.

3.2.4 Training objective

The ability to make the aggregated representation expressive, and capable to be used in KG completion tasks, depends on the training objective. This is designed on top of the path aggregator, and its formulation currently depends on the type of invariance that representations are expected to have. In our case, as the goal is to find missing links in the KG, we focus on *relation prediction* and *true triple classification* as a surrogate task for link prediction. Relation prediction aims at predicting the relation(s) that may exist between head and tail entities – hence completing the triple $(h, ?, t)$. Instead, link prediction is of more general scope, as it aims at predicting either the head entity h given the incomplete triple $(?, r, t)$; or analogously, the tail entity t from $(h, r, ?)$. As introduced in Chapter 1, both these tasks support entity alignment, which can be seen as a specialisation of link and relation prediction when e.g. $r = owl:sameAs$.

To achieve this, we implemented two separate heads on top of the path aggregator, each implementing a training objective. The model is currently trained using one of them, depending to the downstream task. We leave the investigation of both heads for multi-task learning as future work.

3.2.4.1 Relation Prediction Head

Once the relation contextualised representations of the head and tail entities have been obtained, they are concatenated and the resulting matrix $\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{R}^{Z \times 2d}$ is passed through a linear layer which outputs a score matrix $\mathbf{S} \in \mathbb{R}^{Z \times |\mathcal{R}|}$ containing the score of each $(head, tail)$ for each relation. This yields a probability distribution over all the possible relations in the vocabulary $|\mathcal{E}|$, given the head and tail embeddings. Given the (multi-class) classification nature of this task, the relation prediction head use the Cross Entropy loss between the model's prediction and the groundtruth. We remark that Cross Entropy has already been demonstrated to be effective for this task [51].

$$\ell(x, y) = L = \{l_1, \dots, l_N\}^\top, \quad (3.8)$$

$$\text{s.t. } l_n = -w_{y_n} \log \frac{\exp(x_{n,y_n})}{\sum_{c=1}^C \exp(x_{n,c})} \quad (3.9)$$

3.2.4.2 Link Prediction Head

For link prediction, we train for *true triple classification* as a surrogate task. This is implemented by concatenating the head, relation, and tail embeddings in a single tensor of dimension $d \times 3$ representing the whole triple (h, r, t) ; and stacking a fully connected layer for binary classification. In other words, the head predicts whether the triple is in the training set (positive triple) or not (negative triple). Negative triples are constructed by head and tail corruption: the former creates new (negative) triples by replacing h with other entities while keeping relation r and tail t unchanged¹; whereas tail corruptions are created analogously by fixing h, r while changing t .

After sampling N head and N tail corruptions, the model is trained to classify each of them as positive or negative. To balance the classification task, the Binary Cross Entropy loss equally weighs the contribution of positive and the negatives. This is done by dividing the sum of the negative losses by $N \times 2$ following the process used in [16]. In line with the literature, we also experiment with Cross Entropy and the self-adversarial negative sampling loss proposed in [52].

3.3 Experiments

To evaluate our method while accounting for the challenges outlined in Section 1, we propose the following research questions: (**RQ1**, Inductiveness) Can we learn parameter efficient KG embeddings by only encoding relationships? (**RQ2**, Paths) Can we leverage multiple entity-relation paths to encode the KG structure and learn informative representations for link prediction tasks? and (**RQ3**, Suitability) Which properties are expected from a KG to effectively train our model?

To address RQ1, we train a grid of models on common KG benchmark and compare performances with baselines and state-of-the-art embedding methods. Here, we aim at learning KG representations for two main downstream tasks: *transductive link prediction* and *relation prediction*. The goal of the former is to predict heads or tails from incomplete triples, where test/validation entities already occur in the training set. Relation prediction, instead, uses head and tail (entity) embeddings to predict the relation between them.

Multiple configurations of our model with different number of paths and entity aggregation strategies are also tested to trace the contribution of each architectural component related to the use of paths, hence addressing RQ2. Finally, we compare our results to various KG statistics, including relational context, path density and diversity, and provide to gain more insights on the suitability of the model (RQ3).

3.3.1 Experimental setup

In line with the literature, we chose four benchmark datasets to evaluate our model on KGs of various sizes and characteristics.

¹As more triples sharing the same relation and tail may exist in the training set, we always filter the entities in order not to create false negatives (which would also affect the evaluation otherwise).

Dataset	#Ent	#Rel	#Train	#Valid	#Test
FB15K-237	14,505	237	272,115	17,526	20,438
WN18RR	40,559	11	86,835	2,824	2,924
CoDEX-L	77,951	69	551,193	30,622	30,622
YAGO3-10	123,143	37	1,079,040	4,978	4,982

Table 3.1: Number of entities, relations, training, validation, and test triples in the datasets.

- FB15k-237 [53] is derived from Freebase [54] – a large collaborative KG that is now part of the Google Knowledge Graph and preceded Wikidata (two example of large scale KGs). The benchmark counts 15K entities and uses a vocabulary of 237 relations.
- YAGO3-10 [55] is a subset of YAGO3 where entities have a minimum of 10 relations each. It mostly covers attributes of persons such as citizenship, gender, and profession, with 120K+ entities and 37 relations.
- CoDEX-Large [56] is a partition of Wikidata that was specifically designed to cover more diverse content, and provide a more difficult benchmark for link prediction. It contains 78K entities and uses 69 relations.
- WN18RR [55] is a subset of WordNet [57], a lexical taxonomy linking words to their synonyms, hyponyms, and meronyms. The taxonomy counts 40K+ entities and uses a vocabulary of 11 relations.

For all the datasets, we do not use inverse relations, which are usually added to increase the connectivity of the KGs [58]. General statistics for all benchmarks are given in Table 3.1.

We compare our model with both state-of-the-art and parameter efficient KG embedding models, including RotatE [52], NodePiece [14] and EARL [15], which are introduced in Section 2.

Evaluation. All models are evaluated on link and relation prediction, using the original train, validation, and test splits. We report Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR) and Hits@K in the filtered setting [59]. Both these metrics are computed using the scores of the triples produced by the model and evaluated by the ranking induced from those scores. Hits@K measures the ratio of true triples that are ranked among the top K, whereas the MRR averages the reciprocal ranks of true triples and drops rapidly as the ranks grow. These measures are computed by sampling $N \times 2$ corruptions (negative triples) for each positive: N negatives for head corruptions, by replacing the head with other entities in $|\mathcal{R}|$; and N negatives for tail corruptions, which is analogous to the former case. In our experiments, we use $N = 10,000$ to evaluate our model. Using a large yet representative sample of negatives provides a reasonable approximation of the model’s performance, as argued in [60]. We reuse the `Effi` metric proposed in [15] to quantify the efficiency of models as performance cost. This is calculated as $MRR/M(P)$, where $M(P)$ denotes the number of trainable parameters. For all the compared models, we report parameter count and prediction metrics from their corresponding articles.

Implementation. Our model is implemented in PyTorch v2.1 [61] and use PyTorch Lightning 2.1 and PyKEEN v1.1 [62]. We ran experiments on a machine with an Intel Core i9-13900 processor,

128GB of RAM and one NVIDIA RTX 3090 GPU. All models are trained with an early stopping criterion (patience at 10, min delta at 0) and use 99 negative triples for validation. We are in the process of realising our code at <https://github.com/King-s-Knowledge-Graph-Lab>.

3.3.2 Transductive Link Prediction

We trained a grid of models with the Link Prediction head (c.f. Section 3.2.4.2), and computed MRR and Hits@K by ranking each true (test) triple against all its head and tail corruptions. To find optimal models, we performed random search by sampling 50 configurations from a search space of hyperparameters. This is done only for FB15K-237 and WN18RR due to their size. The best configurations for CoDEx-Large and YAGO 3-10 are informed from the results collected from the aforementioned benchmarks. More details on the search space are given in Table 3.6; whereas the best performing configurations are reported in Table 3.7.

Results are given in Table 3.2 for all benchmarks. Overall, compared to parameter-efficient methods, our model achieves state-of-the-art results on CoDEx-Large, and competitive performance on FB15k-237. More precisely, the MRR on FB15K-237 is only 0.009 less than Nodepiece while using only a tiny fraction of its parameter budget; which confirm our model as the most efficient ($Effi = 1.23$) compared to EARL ($Effi = 0.17$) and NodePiece ($Effi = 0.09$). On CoDEx-Large, our model improves RotatE (a non-parameter-efficient state-of-the-art method) with almost 1/5 of parameters (from 2.1 to 0.44); thus recording $Effi = 0.64$ compared to $Effi = 0.10$ for EARL and $Effi = 0.05$ for Nodepiece. Despite the size of CoDEx-Large (2x more training triples and 5x more entities than FB15k-237) we recall that the parameter budget of our model scales linearly with the number of relations (69 for CoDEx, 237 for FB15K). The doubling of the parameter count of the model trained on CoDEx-Large is due to the use of embeddings of dimensionality $d = 128$ instead of $d = 64$ for Fb15k-237 and the use of double the feedforward neurons in the path modelling transformer. Instead, Nodepiece and EARL are affected by the number of entities, as they both allocate embedding tables for a subset of them (alias reserved entities or anchors). However, we also remark that our model performs poorly on WN18RR (a lexical taxonomy) and YAGO 3-10. We discuss the potential implications and the effectiveness of our model in relation to KG properties in Section 3.3.5; and motivate the suitability in Polifonia in Section 3.4.

	FB15k-237			WN18RR			YAGO3-10			CoDEx-Large		
	P(M)	MRR	Hits@10	P(M)	MRR	Hits@10	P(M)	MRR	Hits@10	P(M)	MRR	Hits@10
RotatE	29.3	0.336	0.532	40.6	0.508	0.612	123.2	0.495	0.670	78.0	0.258	0.387
Nodepiece + Rotate	3.2	0.256	0.420	4.4	0.403	0.515	4.1	0.247	0.488	3.6	0.190	0.313
EARL	1.8	0.310	0.501	3.8	0.440	0.527	3.0	0.302	0.498	2.1	0.238	0.390
Our model	0.20	0.247	0.409	0.53	0.121	0.222	0.66	0.140	0.249	0.44	0.283	0.409

Table 3.2: Transductive link prediction results on all benchmarks. Parameter count, MRR, and Hits@10 for all models are taken from [15] and [14]. The corresponding configuration of our model per benchmark dataset are reported in Table 3.7.

3.3.3 Ablation study

To quantify the contribution of each component in the model, we carried out ablation studies on the best performing benchmarks: FB15K and CoDEX-Large. The ablation dimensions are summarised as follows.

- w/o Node Projector, by replacing the GCN Node Projector (c.f. Section 3.2.1) with the fully connected MLP one that operates directly on the relational context of nodes.
- w/o Multiple paths, where we use only 1 path per entity in the triple (1 for the head, 1 for the tail) sampled randomly. Hence, no aggregation is necessary.
- w/o Entity-focused positional encodings, where positional information is injected by adding the relative position of each element in the path. For example, the first entity in the path adds the embedding associated to position 1, the first relation receives 2, etc. regardless of where the head/tail occurs within the path.

	FB15k-237						CoDEX-Large					
	P(M)	MRR	Hits@1	Hits@3	Hits@5	Hits@10	P(M)	MRR	Hits@1	Hits@3	Hits@5	Hits@10
Our base model	0.93	0.157	0.08	0.173	0.223	0.305	0.66	0.270	0.199	0.297	0.347	0.412
-no edge encoder	0.20	0.247	0.164	0.277	0.331	0.409	0.44	0.283	0.215	0.314	0.356	0.409
-no multiple paths	0.93	0.169	0.103	0.177	0.225	0.302	0.66	0.217	0.145	0.240	0.292	0.371
-no adaptive positionals	0.93	0.155	0.086	0.164	0.214	0.295	0.66	0.250	0.177	0.278	0.329	0.396

Table 3.3: Ablation results on link prediction on FB15K-237 and CoDEX-Large (the best performing datasets), with detailed Hits@N metrics for $N=\{1, 3, 5, 10\}$.

The ablation results are summarised in Table 3.3. Overall, we found the node projector of the base model (c.f. Section 3.2.1) to perform worse than the fully-connected MLP one ($MRR = 0.157$ instead of $MRR = 0.247$ for FB15k-237, and $MRR = 0.27$ instead of $MRR = 0.283$ for CoDEX-Large); although the former slightly improves Hits@10 on CoDEX-Large. We speculate that providing edge-level local structure in the early stages of the model, rather than simply relying on relational contexts, may constrain the representations to be sub-optimal when then aggregating information across several paths. This also suggests that more work is needed to design simpler, yet informative, transformations to build an inductive bias on the local structure of the graph into the model.

On CoDEX-Large, our results also confirm the contribution of using multiple paths per head and tail, rather than relying on a single sequence per entity ($MRR = 0.27$ to $MRR = 0.217$ for CoDEX-Large); while relying on a single sequence per entity is either sufficient on FB15k-237, or necessitates novel path aggregation methods to effectively control the relevance of each sequence for link prediction. Finally, entity-focused positional encodings marginally improve performance on FB15k-237, while achieving a 2% gain on CoDEX-Large.

	FB15k-237			WN18RR		
	P(M)	MRR	Hits@10	P(M)	MRR	Hits@10
RotatE	29	0.905	0.979	41	0.774	0.897
Nodepiece + Rotate	3.2	0.874	0.971	4.4	0.761	0.985
Our model	0.8	0.972	0.998	0.04	0.857	0.987

Table 3.4: Relation prediction results on FB15K-237 and WN18RR. Results from Nodepiece and Rotate are taken from [14], which are only reported for the former datasets.

3.3.4 Relation prediction

To evaluate the representations of our model for relation prediction, we use the associated head described in Section 3.2.4.1. This is only done for FB15k-237 and WN18RR, as these are the only benchmarks where a parameter-efficient method has been evaluated and reported in [14].

Relation prediction results are outlined in Table 3.4. Our model significantly outperforms both parameter-efficient (Nodepiece) and state-of-the-art (RotatE) models on relation prediction, while requiring less than a million parameters for FB15k-237. We also remark that our relation prediction model for WN18RR only has 40K parameters, since it uses an embedding dimension of 32 as increasing the embedding dimension did not bring about any increases in performance, which is substantially lower compared to the other models (2-3 orders of magnitude).

3.3.5 Tracing KG properties for effective representations

The various benchmark datasets that are used for the evaluation of embedding models exhibit very diverse characteristics, both due to the nature of the source KG as well as due to the way the triples have been sampled to create the benchmark. Moreover, we found that in the curation of these datasets, little care has been taken to ensure that the sampled triples retain connectivity patterns such as cliques, connected components etc., of the original KG, which inherently affects methods relying on paths that would be able to learn such patterns.

This diversity is reflected on measurements of the number and distribution of relations, the number of unique relational contexts of nodes and the number and uniqueness of the paths mined from each dataset. Specifically, as seen in Table 3.1, the number of unique relations varies significantly between the datasets with the smaller number being 11 for WN18RR and the largest being 237 for FB15K-237. Even though this is a simple measurement, it has a significant impact on inductive models that only use relations to encode both the relations and entities as it significantly limits their ability to discriminate between entities.

To address this problem and make discriminating between nodes easier, our model utilises the frequency of relations in the relational contexts of each entity, which allows relations that appear multiple times in the context of the entity to be represented by their count instead of a binary 1 or 0. It is evident that this encoding scheme works effectively as the entity degree becomes higher

and the ratio of the relation types in the KG is not too unbalanced.

As shown in Section 3.3.2, despite its parameter efficiency, inherent inductive bias and its state-of-the-art performance on several benchmark datasets, our model performs worse on WN18RR and YAGO3-10. As such, it is of paramount importance to determine what are the characteristics of the datasets that our model performs well at, so that researchers and practitioners can determine the applicability of the method prior to using resources for training a model.

Therefore, we sought to investigate the unique relational contexts of each dataset, the ratios of the relations, the number of paths mined by producing 20 random walks of at most 20 steps around each entity and the proportion of those paths that were unique across the dataset. As seen in Table 3.5, in WN18RR and YAGO3-10 the top two relations account for more than 74% and 64% of the total respectively, making these datasets extremely unbalanced. This, coupled with their small number of relation types (11 and 36) and the average entity degree of 4.28 and 17.52, severely limits the informativeness of unique relational contexts (or unique entity encodings) that exist in the datasets. In particular, the unique relational contexts of WN18RR are 3264, which are used to encode 40559 entities and for YAGO3-10 they are 24500, used to encode 123143 entities. This produces a coverage of 0.080 and 0.198 of the entities respectively.

In comparison, FB15K-237 and CoDEX-Large have a much less unbalanced relation ratio, a larger number of unique relations (237 and 69) and large average entity degrees that amount to 37.5 for FB15K-237 and 14.14 for CoDEX-Large. This brings the unique relational contexts to 13352 for FB15K-237 and 36202 for CoDEX-Large, covering 0.920 and 0.464 of the entities, respectively.

3.4 Suitability of the embedding model in Polifonia

In the following, we discuss the suitability of our embedding method to Polifonia KGs, by relating both their properties and the project's requirements to the features provided by our method.

- The vocabulary of relation types is informative enough to provide reasonable diversity in the relational contexts of entities, and consequently, in the uniqueness of paths originating from the random walks. For example, the Music Meta ontology [63] which is only 1 module of the Polifonia Ontology Network [8], already counts more than 70 object properties. As discussed in Section 3.3.5, having a rich vocabulary is one requirement for the effectiveness of our embeddings for link prediction. However, when approaching the entity alignment problem with relation prediction (c.f. Section 3.2.4), our model provides state-of-the-art performance even with small relation vocabularies with imbalanced use (Section 3.5). This implies that, even when a KG does not exhibit the properties discussed in Section 3.5, entity alignment would still be feasible for given pairs of entities to evaluate for equivalence. This also contributes to the long-term vision of the project, with KGs being contributed in future iterations – and whose properties cannot be fully anticipated. As our experimental results demonstrate that a reasonable level of resilience can be achieved via relation prediction, we expect our method to remain effective also when the KGs are sparsely connected.

- The number of entities is large as some KGs in Polifonia result from the integration of large corpora and databases (e.g. ChoCo [6]) or from the computational analysis of music (e.g. Harmory [7]) or text ([64]). Given that such KGs are also expected to grow as a result of planned future iterations (e.g. new datasets and multimodal data in ChoCo) the reuse of traditional embedding methods would require: (i) high-end computational resources and considerable training times for their reuse; and (ii) re-training all models whenever new entities are contributed to the KG. Instead, the parameter efficiency of our model, together with its inductive features (learning to compute entity embeddings rather than explicitly allocating and learning embedding tables) decrease the computational barriers and enable the applicability of the model even when data is incrementally contributed (rather than making the representations and the model obsolete).
- Furthermore, the ability to link Polifonia KGs with other resources on the Web is another requirement that also contributes to the afterlife of the project – as it makes our resources easier to find and to connect with complementary sources of knowledge that are even beyond the scope of musical heritage. One such example is Wikidata, a collaborative KG which counts 11K+ relation types and 108M+ entities, and has been extensively used for various applications. For example, conversational assistants such as Alexa or Siri operate on Wikidata [65]. Linking to Wikidata via KG embeddings represents an extreme case of the previous point, as the computational requirements of encoding millions of entities would be difficult to sustain even with access to high-end hardware [60]. Nonetheless, once an instance of our embedding model has been trained on Wikidata, the representations can be reused for all source KGs necessitating linking to the former².

In sum, our method provides competitive performance for link and relation prediction while requiring memory complexity that scales linearly with the number of relations, and retaining full inductiveness to process new/unseen entities after training. This makes it possible for pilots to train embedding models on their KGs using consumer-grade hardware, and connect entities across such data sources via link or relation prediction.

3.5 Technical details

3.5.1 Edge Frequency Distribution

An important factor that directly influences the performance of any classification model is the class imbalance of a training set. As we only encode (and predict) relations, this applies to the frequency of use of predicates in training triples, which makes generalisation more difficult. As can be seen in Table 3.5 this is particularly prominent in WN18RR and YAGO 3-10 with two of the relation types accounting for 74.3% and 64.4% of the total respectively. In this settings, the model can find it easy to learn the frequency distribution of relations when trained on relation prediction.

²This is not limited to Wikidata, but is of general applicability to large KGs. We remark that our method is indeed domain-agnostic, as demonstrated by the variety of well-established benchmark KGs in Section 3.3

WN18RR			YAGO 3-10		
Edge ID	Frequency	% of Total	Edge ID	Frequency	% of Total
0	1299	1.5	21	373783	34.64
1	29715	34.2	33	321024	29.75
2	4816	5.5	27	88672	8.21
3	34796	40.1	13	66163	6.13
4	2921	3.4	34	44978	4.16
5	7402	8.5	0	32155	2.98
6	923	1.1	23	32055	2.97
7	629	0.7	18	24068	2.23
8	80	0.1	20	10710	0.99
9	3116	3.6	3	9248	0.85
10	1138	1.3	14	7754	0.71

Table 3.5: Absolute and relative counts of relation occurrences in WN18RR and YAGO 3-10.

3.5.2 Transductive Link Prediction

We provide more details on the experimental setup and the hyper-parameter configuration of the models reported in Section 3.3.2. In particular, Table 3.7 documents the search space we defined for the random search of hyper-parameters. Table 3.7 reports the configuration of the best performing models on each dataset. Due to the size of CoDEx-Large and YAGO 3-10, and the availability of computational resources for our experiments, we remark that random search (with N=50 trials) was carried out only on FB15k-237 and WN18RR – with the best performing models originating from such experiments.

Hyperparameter	Range
Embedding dimension	{64, 128, 256}
# paths per entity	{4, 8, 16, 32}
Pathformer	
Dim feedforward	{64, 128, 256}
# attention heads	{2, 3, 4}
# layers	{2, 3}
Dropout	{0.1, 0.2}
Entity aggregation strategy	{avg, mha}
Loss function	{CE, BCE, NSSA}
Label smoothing	{0, 0.1, 0.01}
# Negative samples	{16, 32, 64, 128}
Optimiser	{Adam}
Learning rate	{0.01, 0.01, 0.005}
Batch size	{64, 128, 256, 512, 1024}
Accumulated batches	{16, 32, 64, 128}

Table 3.6: Our hyperparameter search space for link prediction.

Hyper-Parameter	FB15K-237	WN18RR	CoDEX-L	YAGO 3-10
Embedding dim	64	128	128	128
Projector type	MLP	Edge-GCN	MLP	Edge-GCN
Paths per entity	4	16	16	20
Pathformer dim	64	64	128	256
Pathformer heads	4	4	4	4
Pathformer layers	3	2	2	2
Pathformer dropout	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2
Entity aggregation	avg	avg	avg	avg
Loss function	CE	CE	CE	CE
# Negative samples	32	32	32	49
Learning rate	1e-3	1e-3	1e-3	5e-4
Batch size	128	256	1024	800
Accumulated batches	64	128	32	20
Label smoothing	0	0.1	0	0.01
Parameter count	0.20	0.53	0.44	0.66
Effi = $MRR/P(M)$	0.675	0.601	0.510	0.015

Table 3.7: PathE hyperparameters for transductive link prediction experiments.

4 Creative Influence detection using graph theory

Identifying, capturing and hypothesising the influences of an artist is an important aspect that an art critic considers when analysing an artefact or, in general, the artist themselves [66]. The main difficulty in determining influence lies in the subjective nature of the problem. Identifying the influence of an artist on another artist requires a profound knowledge of both entities, their geographical location, the socio-cultural context in which they lived, the technicalities of their artefacts, and so on. It has been argued that an unambiguous definition of creative influence is problematic [37].

Yet, the importance of capturing and understanding the influences of an artist has a great impact on many pragmatic aspects. [67] analyses the work of 90 pioneers in the abstract art movement. The results provide very strong evidence that the success and fame of an artist are related to their social relationships. While it is true that creativity fosters those relationships, the more an artist gets deeper into a clique formed by other meaningful artists, the more its work is acclaimed by critics. For instance, the success of the band *The Velvet Underground* is often partially associated to their relationship with the artist *Andy Warhol* [68]. While the study focuses on visual arts, the same argument holds for any other artistic endeavour. In music, the importance of the relationships of a musician in its creative process is widely recognised [69, 70]. A popular example is the *teacher-student* relationship, sometimes referred to as *mentor-pupil*. Famous artists are often the students of other famous artists, which results in an inevitable influence on their creative process [42].

To understand the influence on an artist, it is important to take into account its social relationships as well. Most recent approaches, however, use artefact similarity as a proxy for creative influence [32, 33, 34, 35, 36]. While this has resulted in promising outcomes, it neglects the incidence of the social circle, making it impossible to detect influences from artists whose stylistic genres are different. Moreover, by persuading a solely similarity-based approach, it is unfeasible to detect artistic influences between two artists that perform on different domains, such as influences of painters on musicians [71, 68], such as in the example of *The Velvet Underground*.

In this section, we propose a method to predict the influence of musical artists by only taking into account their social network. We design an ontology to model the relationships between artists in an expressive way. Rather than consider them as simple direct relationships we model them as complex situations that involve different agents and concepts. We refactor the data from the Linked Jazz project [72]¹, a Knowledge Graph encoding curated relationship between Jazz musicians (among which creative influence), to comply with our ontology and rely on it as a ground truth to perform influence prediction. We frame influence prediction as a classification task where one has to identify and rank artists according to their likelihood to be influential for a given

¹Retrieved from <https://triplifydb.com/pratt/linked-jazz/>

artist. Our approach is based on techniques from graph theory, namely the f -communicability of a graph [73]. Informally, the f -communicability of a graph provides information on how close two artists are as a function of their connections. The shorter the connections between two artists, the higher their communicability. We consider the f -communicability between nodes i and j as the degree of influence that j has on i or, in other words, how influenced is i with respect to j . Our method assigns a weight to each relation in the Knowledge Graph based on the type of relationship. We approximate the weighting function by maximising the f -communicability between influential relationships asserted in the original Knowledge Graph in an optimisation procedure. We evaluate our results through the use of standard information retrieval measures (MRR, MAP, DCG) and compare our method with baselines that rely on the distribution of the data. The learned weighting function obtains results that are aligned with other relevant studies from the socio-cognitive and psychology fields.

4.1 Methodology

This section provides a detailed description of our method. In Section 4.1.1 we discuss the design and implementation of the ontology. In Section 4.1.2 we describe in detail the algorithm used to compute the influences between entities in the KG. In Section 4.1.3 we describe the procedure designed to learn the weight of each relationship type.

4.1.1 Relationship Ontology

The ontology is built upon the concept of *social relation* from the DOLCE ontology [74]. A *social relation* can be defined as a situation expressed by some source of information ², some participants and a role that qualifies the type of the relation.

Table 4.1

Relationship types in the ontology
Admiration, Fellowship, Bandmate, Copupils, Friendship, Mentorship, Parenthood, Rivalship, Siblinghood

In our ontology, we only take into account pairwise relationships. This is intended as two roles (*source* and *target*) that partake in the relationship. In this way, it is possible to define a relation between sets of entities while retaining the directedness of the relationship. An example is the *Mentorship* relation, where a single mentor might have multiple students. The source of information tracks the provenance of the relationship assertion. The relationship types are described in Table 4.1.

²An information object in DOLCE

Figure 4.1: Ontology in Graffoo syntax. A pairwise relationship involving two agents is reified as a `PersonalRelationship` classified by an arbitrary type and expressed by another entity. A binary projection is automatically inferred using the property chain axiom in the blue box.

Figure 4.1 visually represents the ontology. The class `:PersonalRelationship` reifies the relationship between two agents. To guarantee compactness and easiness of querying, we define the property `:hasPersonalRelationshipWith` to instantiate the binary projection reified by `:PersonalRelationship`. This is defined through the use of property chain axioms (blue box in Figure 4.1). Note that we do not restrict the amount of subjects to the `:hasSource` and `:hasTarget` properties. This enables the representation of pairwise relationships between two sets of entities.

Figure 4.2: Example of the friendship relationship using the ontology. The `FriendshipRelationship` class (left) is constrained to be described by the `Friendship` class. The relationship `<Trent Reznor, :hasFriend, David Bowie>` is represented on the right. The red colour (bottom right) identifies the inferred axioms and entities. Dashed arrows are refinement additions. The property `:R_FriendshipRelationship` (top left) is used to express class membership in property chain axioms using the rolification technique.

In Figure 4.2 an example of how the ontology can be used to define the friendship relationship of Table 4.1 is described. In order to define a friendship relationship be-

tween the musicians *Trent Reznor* and *David Bowie* it is sufficient to add the triple $\langle \text{Trent Reznor}, \text{:hasFriend}, \text{David Bowie} \rangle$ in the Knowledge Graph. The reification of the relationship is automatically performed by the inference engine.

The implemented reification allows us to represent the relationship as a whole rather than flattening it into a binary relation, resulting in a richer characterisation of the relationship and a high degree of control in further refining it. For example, in Figure 4.2 the dashed properties represent refinement operations over the initial definition. It is possible to classify the relationship as both a friendship and mentorship relationship while adding documents that act as references to back up the assertion.

4.1.2 f -communicability as influence indicator

Once relations are represented using the ontology described in Section 4.1.1, the resulting Knowledge Graph can be interpreted as a semantically defined social network. By only relying on the binary projections of the reified relationships we can extract a directed graph G where entities are directly connected to each other by means of a set of edges E . In order to quantify the influence of one artist on another, we exploit tools that pertain to the analysis of complex networks.

Our approach is based on the f -communicability [73] of the nodes in a graph, which is defined as a function of the paths that connect two distinct nodes. Generally, a node is *highly communicative* with another node if there are many paths that connect the two nodes. The length of the connecting path is an important factor that needs to be considered. If information (e.g. creative influence) has to travel in the graph, a shorter path is much more convenient than a longer one. This means that artists are generally influenced by close connections. Nonetheless, long connections should not be ignored. The f -communicability score between two connected nodes changes as a function of the length of the path: the shorter the path, the higher the communicability of the nodes.

In Figure 4.3 a visual example of the communicability between artists and the importance of the length of the path is reported.

We rely on f -communicability as an indicator of how influential an artist is with respect to the other artists in the Knowledge Graph. We define a Knowledge Graph KG as a directed edge-labelled graph $G = (V, E, L)$ where V represents the set of nodes in the graph, E the set of edges and L the set of labels that can be assigned to an edge $e \in E$. L is effectively the set of binary projections obtained from the relationship types of Table 4.1.

The f -communicability between nodes i, j in a graph G is computed as $f(A)_{ij}$ where f is a suitable matrix function and A is the adjacency matrix of G . In order to take into account the different importance of the relationship types $l \in L$ we use a weighting function $w : L \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_0^+$. The function w can be interpreted as the absolute degree of importance of a relationship type and can either be predefined or learned, as we show in section 4.1.3. We can now define the weighted adjacency matrix A as

$$A_{ij} = \sum_{l \in \text{labels}(i,j)} w(l) \quad (4.1)$$

Figure 4.3: Example of social graph. Intuitively, the communicability between *Halsey* and *David Bowie* should be high given the direct and non-direct connections. Nonetheless, the communicability with *Pete Townshend* should be considered as well, since there is a chain of relations that connects the two artists.

where $labels(i, j)$ is the set of labels of the edges between i and j .

The f -communicability $f(i, j)$ between the nodes $i, j \in V$ is computed as

$$f(i, j) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \alpha_k (A^k)_{ij} \tag{4.2}$$

where A^n is the n -th power of A , and α_k is a weight assigned to the walks of length k . Given an adjacency matrix A of a graph G , the entry $(A^k)_{ij}$ is equal to the sum of the weights of all walks in G from node i to node j of length exactly k [75].

The weight α_k defines how the importance of a walk should decay as a function of its length and needs to be carefully chosen in order to make sure that the sum of Equation 4.2 converges to the finite value. This is done by using a succession (α_k) converging to 0 [73]. This ensures that walks of length ∞ will have a null weight. The choice of how α_k should decay leads to the use of different functions [76, 77]. We follow the definition of [77] and set $\alpha_k = \frac{1}{k!}$. Our function f is hence the exponential matrix function. Given the computational cost of obtaining the exact exponential function (particularly for large graphs), we define our actual f -communicability function as an approximation of the exponential matrix function. This is done by truncating the

Figure 4.4: Examples of equation 4.3 computed on the example from Figure 4.3. The labels *TD*, *DB*, *BE*, *TR* and *H* are used to represent the nodes of, respectively, Pete Townshend, Brian Eno, David Bowie, Trent Reznor and Halsey. For simplicity of understanding the weights of equation 4.1 are considered to be $w(l) = 1 \quad \forall l \in L$. Relations that represent direct influence (e.g. $H \rightarrow DB$) are not added to the graph. In Figure a the adjacency matrix obtained from Equation 4.1 is shown. Note that the nodes that have redundant connections (e.g. $DB \rightarrow TR$) have a value of 2. In Figure b the f -communicability function is computed for walks of length 1. Nodes that were previously disconnected (e.g. $TR \rightarrow PT$) are now connected. The same happens in Figure c, except that new connections have a lower weight (e.g. $H \rightarrow PT$).

power series that represents such a function. Formally, we compute

$$f^D(i, j) = \sum_{k=1}^D \frac{(A^k)_{ij}}{k!} \tag{4.3}$$

where D is a parameter corresponding to the maximum length of a walk taken into account by f^D . An approximation of the centrality of a node $i \in G$ can be obtained by computing $f^D(i, i)$. See Figure 4.4 for an example on how Equation 4.3 is computed based on Figure 4.3.

4.1.3 Learning the importance of a relationship

One requirement of the method just described is that the graph from which the influence is predicted is weighted.

Defining the weight of a social relationship is an elaborate task, particularly when it needs to be contextualised in the creative domain. [44] argues on the existence of strong and weak social ties and their influence on creativity. Strong ties, defined as highly redundant connections between two individuals (e.g. *Trent Reznor* and *David Bowie* in Figure 4.3) are found to positively correlate with creativity. A straightforward approach, which will serve as a baseline, is to assign to each relation type the same weight (e.g. 1) by using $w : L \rightarrow 1$. However, it is important to note that not all relationships equally correlate with creativity [42]. Given a reference KG, a distributional approach can be taken by defining the weight of the label to be (inversely) proportional to their distribution in the graph. This can be done by defining $w(l) = \frac{|E_l|}{|E|}$ (respectively $w(l) = \frac{|E|}{|E_l|}$)

where $E_l = \{e \in E \text{ s.t. } l \in \text{labels}(e)\}$. This approach assumes that the importance of a relationship is (inversely) proportional to the distribution of that same relationship among the reference population. While this might be true, KG relies on the open-world assumption, where data incompleteness is taken into account. This is an important aspect since it is difficult (if not impossible) to completely enumerate the social relationships of an individual.

We propose to learn the weights assigned by w by fitting the data in the knowledge graph. This can be obtained by framing the problem of predicting creative influence as a multi-class classification problem. Given an edge $e = (i, j)$ we can interpret $f^D(i, j)$ as the probability that $e \in E$ with $l \in \text{labels}(e)$ where l is the label assigned to the edges that semantically states that i is creatively influenced by j . Essentially, the f -communicability of a pair of nodes (i, j) measures the degree to which i is creatively influenced by j .

In order to do that we minimise the cross entropy-based learning-to-rank loss defined in [78] between $f^D(\hat{A}_{ij})$ and A_{tij} where t is the label assigned to the relationship that represents the influence of an artist onto another artist and $\hat{A}_{ij} = \sum_{l \in Lt} A_{lij}$. By relying on a learning-to-rank loss we learn weights in such a way that, given an input artist, its most influential artists are given a high weight. As a result, the model will be able to rank other artists in a meaningful way despite the absence of any explicit edge in the original graph.

While aggregating relations as in Equation 4.1 is a natural and straightforward approach, it is reasonable to suppose that the joint presence of two relationships, e.g. *friendship* and *mentorship* together, might be more (or less) important than the sum of the two components. To take this additional consideration into account we perform a non-linear combination using a feedforward neural network with one hidden layer using a ReLU activation. Equation 4.1 is hence updated to

$$A_{ij} = NN([A_{tij} \quad \forall t \in L]) \quad (4.4)$$

with NN being the function learned by the neural network.

4.2 Experiments

We rely on the data from the Linked Jazz project [72]. Linked Jazz is a Knowledge Graph containing information about famous jazz musicians and their social connections to other musicians. Data is semi-automatically annotated from the transcription of artists' interviews using crowd-sourced annotations. While some relationship types are objective (e.g. *bandmate* relationship) some have a subjective definition (e.g. *influence* relationship) and needs to be interpreted in the context of the interview. Annotators are provided with a definition for each relationship type, which partly addresses this issues. Modelling social relations as linked open data has shown how it is possible to uncover meaningful relationships between entities that are otherwise difficult to uncover [45].

We align the Linked Jazz KG to our ontology (described in Section 4.1.1) through the use of a SPARQL construct query.

Figure 4.5: Relation distribution in the KG.

The KG contains a total of 5058 statements between 70 artists, where each musician has 72 relations asserted on average. In Figure 4.5 the distribution of the relationship between the entities in the KG is shown.

4.2.1 Experimental setup

In order to learn the weights of the function w of Equation 4.1 we split the data into the usual training and testing partitions, where the testing partition is 20% of the total data. The resulting training and testing data are hence composed of, respectively, 56 and 14 artists. Since the amount of explicitly stated influences available in the KG is much lower than the total amount of edges, the split is only based on nodes that have some influence edges asserted. This allows us to effectively evaluate the accuracy of the model with respect to creative influence prediction. Given the small size of both splits, we evaluate the models on aggregate values from a set of 5 distinct experiments on different subsets of the data. This helps us mitigate the noise due to the low amount of data available.

We evaluate each model using Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR), Mean Average Precision (MAP) and Discounted Cumulative Gain (DCG). All the listed metrics measure how high are ranked appropriate values, e.g. how high are ranked actual influential artists with respect to a reference artist. MRR can be interpreted as how far is the first influential artist in the ordered list. MAP is the average of the number of relevant entries within the first k results, where k is the number of influences of each artist. DCG evaluates the results by penalising when relevant entries are not positioned at the top of the list. Each model is trained using COCOB [79], a parameter-free optimisation method. All the experiments are performed on an Intel i9 with 128GB of RAM and an Nvidia RTX3090 with 24GB of VRAM.

Figure 4.6: Aggregate value combining all methods as a function of the variable D in Equation 4.2.

4.3 Results

In Figure 4.6 results from all methods are aggregated and plotted as a function of the degree D of Equation 4.2. The results highlight how using walks whose length extends at most up to 2 nodes obtains the best results. Influences from artists that are difficult to reach, i.e. that are separated by many other nodes, add noise to the f -communicability matrix. In fact, [44] argues that creative influence can be classified into two main categories: *strong* and *weak* influence, where *strong* influence, as opposed to *weak* influence, is the result of many redundant connections between two nodes. In other words, the influence of an artist on another artist is stronger if the amount of connections between the two is high. Taking into account long walks results in many connections that eventually turn a weak influence into a strong one. This can also be seen in the example of Figure 4.2. The influence of *Pete Townshend* on *Halsey* can be safely ignored. Taking into account walks longer than degree 2 wrongly detects this relationship as a *strong* one. In Equation 4.2 longer walks are considered less important. However, this proves not to be enough, as the number of distinct longer walks from two entities mitigates this discount and results in less accurate predictions. Further investigation on other converging series used for decaying weights can result in more accurate performances.

Table 4.2 reports the results obtained from the experiments of Section 4.2 with $D = 2$. Learning the function w used in Equation 4.3 leads to the best results on aggregate with respect to all the metrics taken into account. Surprisingly, using a neural network as illustrated in Equation 4.4 does not result in a definite gain with respect to the simpler model of Equation 4.1. The main reason for that is the lack of training data. The network is not able to generalise over the target task and tends to overfit in the training data despite the small number of parameters.

In Table 4.3 the weights learned by the best method of Table 4.2 are described. Judging from the mean and median values, the most important relationships are the *friendship* and *mentorship*

Table 4.2: Result from the experiment described in Section 4.2. Each value is reported alongside its standard deviation.

w	MAP	DCG	MRR
Uniform	0.23 ± 0.13	0.48 ± 0.13	0.43 ± 0.24
Frequency	0.17 ± 0.12	0.43 ± 0.12	0.28 ± 0.23
Inverse Frequency	0.23 ± 0.16	0.49 ± 0.16	0.43 ± 0.27
Learned	0.28 ± 0.13	0.53 ± 0.11	0.50 ± 0.17
DNN	0.1 ± 0.17	0.3 ± 0.19	0.16 ± 0.27

Table 4.3: Statistics on the learned weights from the best model of table 4.2.

Relationship	$\max(w)$	$\text{mean}(w)$	$\text{median}(w)$	$\min(w)$
has acquaintance	9.456889	9.244201	9.286146	8.995128
has bandmate	9.958392	7.067571	6.286661	6.230026
has friend	15.739528	14.435940	14.669381	13.340489
has mentor	4.089674	3.709073	3.636836	3.510836
has pupil	12.359836	10.432499	11.434330	6.429887
is friend of	4.090974	3.709161	3.636191	3.510761

relationship. The former aligns with the findings of [67]: the influences of famous artists can be largely associated with the connections they have with other meaningful artists from the same clique. Moreover, it is important to notice how the inverse relationship, *is friend of*, has a lower weight when compared to the *has friend* relationship. In order to understand this phenomenon it is sufficient to contextualise it in the task we have identified. An artist can be influenced by a friend only if the artist itself acknowledges that relationship. If the relationship is asymmetric, i.e. one of the two artists is unaware of it, the influence between the two should be much weaker. An interesting phenomenon happens with the *mentorship* relationship. Artists are much more influenced by their students (*has pupil* relationship) rather than their mentors. This is a direct result of taking into account relationships that span multiple edges rather than a direct connection. Even though an artist can be influenced by one of its students, we argue that the result of the high weight is explained best by a *co-pupil* relationship. An artist is influenced by another artist when they both share the same mentor. This aligns with the findings of [42], where mentors are seen as a *bridge* between two artists.

5 Compliance to the FAIR principles

This section encompasses information which helps to the knowledge management in the project and to make Polifonia FAIR (operating according to principles of Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This ensures compliance with the guidelines and principles of the Polifonia Data Management Plan (v2.0) [80]. We remind the Polifonia 10 Rules for Open Science from D7.2 [80] as follows.

- R1: Polifonia requires that all essential components of the Polifonia Ecosystem are registered in the Polifonia Github community.
- R2: Polifonia recommends to use Zenodo to register output.
- R3: Organise access to your resources via the Polifonia Portal/Polifonia server.
- R4: Use your ORCID to identify you as an author!
- R5: Acknowledge the grant (the Polifonia project) with each output!
- R6: Use DOI's to refer to work you produce!
- R7: For datasets you think are important cornerstones of your work deposit them into the Polifonia Ecosystem (see R1). Consider archiving 'authoritative versions' into a certified data repository!
- R8: Authorship/publication Netiquette
- R9: R9: Adhere FAIR principles and licencing principles
- R10: If in doubt: Ask the Data Managers of your institutions and consult the Data Stewards of Polifonia.

5.1 KG Embedding model – Software

We have implemented a number of actions to ensure that these outputs are in compliance with the FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship [81]. In particular, we commit to share all code, data, and related resources online at <https://github.com/King-s-Knowledge-Graph-Lab>. This includes model checkpoints and pre-trained embeddings, so that users can easily extract the representations learned from the benchmark datasets presented in Section 3.3. The latest versions of our model will be available on Zenodo, in synchronisation with GitHub releases for consistent versioning. Via GitHub and Zenodo, our project has a unique and persistent identifier and is registered in a searchable source. Through the addition of YAML metadata according to the Polifonia Ecosystem rulebook¹, the model will also be integrated within the Ecosystem automatically through its future releases with well-described,

¹<https://github.com/polifonia-project/rulebook>

Requirement	Options	Outcome
Polifonia 10 Rules	None, R1, R2, ... , R10	R1, R3, R4, R5, R8, R9, R10
GitHub link	None, Link	On request
Zenodo link	None, Link	N.A.
Ecosystem integration	Yes, Planned, N/A	Planned
PON Alignment	Full, Partial, Planned, N/A	Full
License	License	MIT
Deployment link	Link, N/A, Planned	Planned

Table 5.1: Overview of FAIRness coverage for our KG embedding method

machine-processable metadata from various interoperable schemas. Furthermore, being integrated as part of the Polifonia Ecosystem, all data and metadata produced use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.

5.2 Influence prediction model – Software

Requirement	Options	Outcome
Polifonia 10 Rules	None, R1, R2, ... , R10	R1, R3, R4, R5, R8, R9, R10
GitHub link	None, Link	Github link
Zenodo link	None, Link	N.A.
Ecosystem integration	Yes, Planned, N/A	Planned
PON Alignment	Full, Partial, Planned, N/A	Full
License	License	CC-BY
Deployment link	Link, N/A, Planned	N.A.

Table 5.2: Overview of FAIRness coverage for our influence prediction method

Similarly to the KG embedding model, the implemented actions ensures that these outputs are in compliance with the FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship [81].

6 Conclusions

This deliverable advances the vision of the INTERLINK pilot, by contributing scalable and parameter-efficient knowledge graph embedding models for relation and link prediction. The general applicability of our model and the low parameter budget required, make it particularly suitable to large knowledge graphs where new entities are introduced over time. Compared to previous approaches, our model does not explicitly allocate and learn embedding tables for entities, but is trained to compute them – using relational context and path-level information. Given a triple, the model receives a set of entity-relation paths for the head and the tail; contextualise the sequential data using self-attention networks and aggregates the representations across the different paths to yield an embedding vector for each entity. Embeddings are trained using two separate heads, each entailing a classification task that directly or indirectly (as a surrogate) address relation prediction and link prediction, respectively.

To evaluate our model consistently with the literature, we separately train for relation and link prediction on four benchmark datasets of various size and properties (FB15k-237, WN18RR, CoDEx-Large, YAGO 3-10); and measure performance via Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR) and Hits@K metrics. Our results show that, using less than a million parameters and training on consumer-grade hardware, our model achieves state of the art results for relation prediction and competitive performance for link prediction. In addition, we perform ablation studies to quantify the contribution of the main architectural components of the model, and find that using multiple paths for computing entity-level embeddings yields better performance compared to our baselines. We also find that our model performs best on KGs with a large vocabulary size and diverse relational contexts, which directly impacts on the uniqueness of paths and hence the potential ability of the model to reconstruct the identity of each entity from them. In attempt to explain the behaviour of our model on the benchmark, we relate our MRR with KG-specific properties, and speculate how the effectiveness of our method is affected by the use of relations. Finally, we offer insights into the applicability of the model to Polifonia and the relevance of our strengths (mainly, parameter efficiency and inductiveness) to the peculiarities of the KGs and challenges of the project.

We are currently working on improving the generalisation capabilities of our embedding model across various tasks, while testing new training objectives for foundational KG embedding models – e.g. by leveraging both relation and link prediction heads in a multi-task learning settings. As future work, we plan to train our model on a sample that contains a representative partition of the musical knowledge in Wikidata¹; and explore how the effectiveness of the learned representation after new triples are incrementally added. Given the scalability feature, this will allow the linkage of arbitrary (Music) Knowledge Graphs to Wikidata, which also contributes to the afterlife of the

¹Note that CoDEx-Large is already sampled from Wikidata and contains triples expressing musical knowledge, as per [56]. Hence, our goal is to increase the size and coverage of this subset to measure our performances.

project.

On the other hand, the influence prediction method allows the detection of creative influence between artists using techniques based on graph theory and complex network science. Our method takes into account the individuality of a relationship type. By framing the influence prediction task as a classification task we are able to obtain an interpretable model that performs better than robust baselines. The results highlight how a straightforward combination of the different graph planes identified by the different relationship types results in accurate results. Moreover, the weights assigned to each relationship type are in line with relevant socio-cognitive and psychological findings, thus additionally validating the results. Our attempt to increase the accuracy of our results through the use of a machine learning approach led to less accurate predictions. Nonetheless, it is difficult to objectively rule out the possibility of combining machine learning techniques with our methods. In future works, we plan on extending the dataset available. The main problem with the experiments relying on the neural network can indeed be partially caused by the limited amount of training data for the model. An approach is to employ data augmentation techniques, in order to exploit the data as much as possible and reduce the chances of overfitting the model. With the availability of additional data, for instance by using relation extraction methods [82, 83, 84], more complex architectures can also be used, such as attention-based models [85]. Finally, we would like to explore clustering methods and detect communities of artists within the f -communicability matrix. This would enable the identification of cliques of artists that are socially related and hence provide a tool to better understand the creative process of an artist. Combining the relationship types with additional relevant information, such as the socio-cultural context [40], is also an interesting improvement worth investigating. Similarly, combining our approach with the one identified by [33], where influence between artists is modelled on the basis of the similarity between their artefacts, is an interesting approach as it could help increase the accuracy while also providing examples of artefacts where such similarities can be identified.

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